

FURTHER CHEMICAL EVIDENCES REGARDING THE RELATIVE POSITION OF DOUBLE BOND AND KETO GROUP IN ARTOSTENONE

BY M. C. NATH AND M. K. CHAKRABORTY

A new derivative of artostenone,—dihydroxy-artostenone—has been prepared, the formation of which, according to Butenandt gives additional support to the view that artostenone is an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone. 2 : 4-Di-nitrophenylhydrazone of artostenone has also been prepared.

The structure of artostenone (I), the steroid ketone isolated from the unsaponifiable matter of the latex of Indian summer fruit *Artocarpous integrifolia*, has been based on chemical as well as X-ray data, previously presented (Nath, *Z. Physiol. Chem.*, 1937, 247, 16 ; 249, 71, 78 ; Nath and Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 229). Butenandt *et al* (*Ber.*, 1935, 71B, 1483) have shown that cholestenone, an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone, undergoes oxidation with hydrogen peroxide in presence of osmic acid and forms dihydroxycholestanone. Applying the same reaction artostenone is converted into dihydroxy-artostenone (II), though hydrogen peroxide alone has got no action on the former. Petro and Starling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 60) have recently shown that Δ^5 -cholestene-3 : 4-dione, an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone, forms 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone with Bredig's reagent (2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine). By application of the same method a corresponding derivative of artostenone has also been prepared.

(I)
Artostenone.

(II)
Dihydroxy-artostenone.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation of Dihydroxyartostenone.—Artostenone (2 g.) was dissolved in ether (100 c.c.) and treated with osmic acid (0.1 g.) in 10 c.c. of ether. 30 c.c. of perhydrol were then added to the mixture and the latter was allowed to remain for 20 hours at ordinary temperature. The resulting solution was then evaporated completely and dried without application of heat, until the odour of osmic acid was removed. It was once again dissolved in ether and decolourised with 1 or 2 drops of perhydrol and evaporated. The colourless semicrystalline residue (1.8 g.) after several crystallisation gave a beautiful 6-sided crystalline substance (0.4 g.) m.p., 141-42°. (Found : C, 78.32 ; H, 11.27. $C_{28}H_{44}O_3$ requires C, 78.26 ; H, 11.30 per cent).

Acetate of Dihydroxyartostenone.—Dihydroxyartostenone (0.05 g.) was dissolved in a few drops of pyridine and refluxed for 12 minutes on a sand-bath with a few drops of acetic anhydride. It was then cooled, poured into water and extracted with ether; ether was evaporated off and the residue crystallised several times from methyl alcohol,

m.p. 89-90°. (Found : C, 74'91; H, 10'32. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 75'0, H, 10'29 per cent).

Oxime of Dihydroxyartostenone.—An alcoholic solution of dihydroxyartostenone (0'1 g.) and 0'05 g. of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and an excess of sodium acetate was refluxed for 15 minutes on a water-bath, cooled, diluted with water and shaken with ether in a separating funnel. The ethereal layer was separated and ether evaporated off. The solid residue was crystallised repeatedly from absolute alcohol as needles, m.p. 215-16°. (Found : N, 2'88. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4N$ requires N, 2'94 per cent).

The Semicarbazone.—An alcoholic solution of dihydroxyartostenone and an aqueous alcoholic solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and an excess of sodium acetate were refluxed for 6 hours on a water-bath, cooled and poured into water. The precipitate was filtered, washed repeatedly with water and finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 178-80°. (Found : C, 71'88 ; H, 10'70. $C_{21}H_{24}O_4N_2$ requires C, 71'95 ; H, 10'63 per cent).

The 2 : 4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of Artostenone.—An alcoholic solution of artostenone (0'2 g.) and of 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0'2 g.) was boiled with a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid, when 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of artostenone was precipitated. It was filtered, washed and dried. The total yield was 0'32 g. It was crystallised from benzene-alcohol mixture (4 : 1) as flowery orange red crystals, m.p. 228-29°. (Found : N, 9'05. $C_{28}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires N, 9'24 per cent).

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY.

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